

Correlation between C677T and A1298C *MTHFR* polymorphisms and non-obstructive azoospermia in Bulgarian patients

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Abstract

We have analyzed the following polymorphisms: C677T (rs 1801133) and A1298C (rs 1801131) in the methylenetetrahydrofolate reductase (*MTHFR*) gene in Bulgarian patients with non-obstructive azoospermia, attending reproductive clinics. We have compared the allele and genotype frequencies of both the *MTHFR* C677T and A1298C polymorphisms in our population to the European population and to a Bulgarian control group (n = 350). The results of our research have revealed a trend for a significantly higher frequency of the homozygote C/C genotype of *MTHFR* A1298C polymorphism in comparison to the European and Bulgarian controls (p < 0.08). The prevalence of the C/C homozygotes can be accepted as a risk factor for the development of non-obstructive azoospermia, especially in addition to other external and internal factors—diet, vitamin intake, other genetic polymorphisms or mutations in the genes involved in spermatogenesis.

Keywords

methylenetetrahydrofolate reductase, pharmacogenetic polymorphisms, male infertility

Introduction

Azoospermia is considered the most severe form of male infertility. It is established in 1% of the world population (Cocuzza et al. 2013; Agarwal et al. 2015) and in 10–15% of infertile men (Cocuzza et al. 2013; Sharma and Leslie 2024). In the majority of azoospermic patients, a non-obstructive form of azoospermia has been established (Sharma and Leslie 2024). In approximately 30% of the cases, the etiology of azoospermia remains unclear (Kamiński et al. 2020). Evidence is currently accumulating for the significance of some polymorphisms in the genes involved in

testicular function and their role as a contributing factor for the development of non-obstructive azoospermia (Kim et al. 2015). The aim of the current study is to determine the association between the most common *MTHFR* polymorphisms (C677T and A1298C) and severe spermatogenic failure in patients attending reproductive clinics.

Methylenetetrahydrofolate reductase (*MTHFR*) is a key regulatory enzyme in the 1-carbon metabolism that catalyzes the reduction of 5,10-methylenetetrahydrofolate to 5-methyltetrahydrofolate. 5-methyltetrahydrofolate is required for the synthesis of S-adenosylmethionine (SAM), the major donor of methyl groups for

methyltransferase enzymes (Shen et al. 2011; Eloualid et al. 2012; Singh and Jaiswal 2012; Guillems 2018; Al-Janaibi et al. 2022). Reduced concentrations of SAM lead to alterations in DNA and histone methylation, which have a long-term effect on epigenetic regulation (Guillems 2018). Disruptions in the process of DNA methylation can lead to latent transposons activation, chromosome breakage, and genomic instability (Singh and Jaiswal 2012; Rotondo et al. 2021). In addition, the accumulation of homocysteine observed in *MTHFR* deficiency leads to an increased generation of reactive oxygen species that induce DNA fragmentation and lipid peroxidation, affecting the vitality of male germ cells (Aitken et al. 2016). Research on animal models has revealed that the activity of the enzyme is five times higher in the male gonads than in other tissues (Chen et al. 2001; Eloualid et al. 2012). It was also established that the inactivation of the *MTHFR* gene in male mice leads to infertility, absence of germinal cells, and spermatogenic arrest (Kelly et al. 2005; Khazamipour et al. 2009; Wu et al. 2010; Gupta et al. 2011). Thus, *MTHFR* is considered an essential enzyme involved in the process of spermatogenesis, and its polymorphisms in men with spermatogenic failure are worth investigation.

The two most common and well-studied polymorphic variants of the *MTHFR* gene are C677T (rs 1801133) and A1298C (rs 1801131). In the C677T polymorphism, cytosine substitutes thymine at position 677, and alanine is replaced by valine in the catalytic site of the enzyme (Botto et al. 2000; Yang et al. 2007; Gupta et al. 2011). As a result, the affinity of *MTHFR* to the cofactor flavin adenine dinucleotide (FAD) is reduced, and the stability of the enzyme is altered. The activity of the enzyme is reduced by 35% in C/T heterozygotes and by 70% in the mutant T/T homozygote genotype compared to the wild type (Yang et al. 2007; Gupta et al. 2011). The A1298C polymorphism results from the transition of adenosine to cytosine and a substitution of glutamic acid for alanine in the protein structure. This leads to the synthesis of an enzyme with reduced activity by 15% for the A/C heterozygotes and by 30% for the C/C homozygotes. Both polymorphisms are related to certain human diseases, including cardiovascular disorders, some types of cancer, and infertility (Botto et al. 2000). Furthermore, *MTHFR* polymorphisms lead or contribute to changes in the metabolism of a variety of xenobiotics, including drugs, and exert direct and indirect effects in drug response. It was established that patients with *MTHFR* deficiency are more vulnerable to the adverse effects of a number of drugs such as antifolates (methotrexate, raltitrexed), antiepileptic drugs (carbamazepine and phenytoin), antiparkinsonian drugs (levodopa), antidepressants, and neuroleptics (Schwahn et al. 2013) that are commonly used in clinical practice. Analyzing the *MTHFR* polymorphisms and personalized treatment based on genotype testing can help to predict and significantly decrease the risk of adverse drug reactions and toxicity.

Materials and methods

We have analyzed *MTHFR* polymorphisms in 72 infertile men attending reproductive clinics. Non-obstructive azoospermia was established in all patients. Semen was obtained by masturbation after 2–5 days of ejaculatory abstinence. Semen analyses were performed in a computer-assisted sperm analysis system (CASA). Reference values from the WHO 1999 manual were used for the interpretation of the semen results (because of the controversies surrounding the 2010 WHO criteria and until 2021, when new reference values were introduced). Conditions such as varicocele, cryptorchidism, microdeletions of the Y chromosome, and the absence of ductus deference were excluded as causes of azoospermia in these patients. DNA was isolated from peripheral blood samples by a standard salting method. We performed a multiplex RT-PCR using the kit *MTHFR* mpx RealFast™ Assay for the simultaneous detection of C677T and A1298C polymorphisms in the *methylene-tetrahydrofolate reductase (MTHFR)* gene in our patients. The PCR test was based on the TaqMan assay (fluorogenic 5' nuclease assay). Each reaction contained two gene-specific primer pairs that amplified a 144 bp and a 185 bp fragment of the *MTHFR* gene and four dual-labeled, allele-specific hydrolysis probes that were specifically hybridized to the target sequences of the amplified fragments. From the hybridized probes, the 5'-fluorescent reporter was cleaved by the TaqMan DNA polymerase, generating a fluorescent signal proportional to the amplified PCR products. The signal was generated in a specific channel, responding to a wild type or a mutant allele, respectively, detected by the PCR software. The allele and genotype frequencies were compared with the data from the Ensembl genome database and an internal database for Bulgarian individuals from the Molecular Medicine Center, Medical University of Sofia.

Results

We have compared the allele and genotype frequencies of both the *MTHFR* C677T and A1298C polymorphisms in the Bulgarian patients with non-obstructive azoospermia to the European population and a Bulgarian control group (n = 350). The allele frequency is represented in Fig. 1—there was an increase in the C1298 allele frequency in our patients, not reaching statistical significance. There were no significant differences in the genotype prevalence of *MTHFR* C677T polymorphism in the Bulgarian men with azoospermia compared to the European and Bulgarian controls, as depicted in Fig. 2.

We established a trend for a significantly higher frequency of the homozygote C/C genotype of *MTHFR* A1298C polymorphism in comparison to the European and Bulgarian controls—17% in our patients compared to 10% and 8% in the European and Bulgarian controls, respectively ($p < 0.08$)—illustrated in Fig. 3. The prevalence of C/C homozygotes (A1298C) can be accepted as a risk factor for the development of non-obstructive azoospermia and male infertility.

Figure 1. The allele frequencies of *MTHFR* C677T and A1298C polymorphisms in Bulgarian azoospermic men compared to the Bulgarian and European controls.

Figure 2. Genotype frequency of the *MTHFR* C677T polymorphism.

Figure 3. Genotype frequency of the *MTHFR* A1298C polymorphism among Bulgarian men with non-obstructive azoospermia.

Discussion

Spermatogenesis is a complex process in which multiple genes are involved (Botto et al. 2000; Tanoomand et al. 2019). Some of them encode for regulatory enzymes, taking part in the one-carbon metabolism. Folate metabolism

is essential for DNA synthesis, DNA methylation, and repair, providing DNA integrity and stability during spermatogenesis (Murphy et al. 2011; Vazharova et al. 2016; Raigani et al. 2021). As a key regulatory enzyme in the folate and methionine cycles, the activity of *MTHFR* is essential for proper testicular function. Evidence is currently accumulating for the impact of two *MTHFR* polymorphisms, C677T and A1298C, as risk factors for the development of spermatogenic failure. A significant association between the *MTHFR* C677T polymorphism and male infertility was determined by various authors (Tüttelmann et al. 2007; Gupta et al. 2011; Wu et al. 2012; Gong et al. 2015), while others excluded such correlations (Wei et al. 2011). Yang et al. (2007) determined the C677T polymorphism as a genetic risk factor for azoospermia or severe oligozoospermia in the Chinese population. According to research data, a link between male infertility and C677T polymorphism was established in the Asian population but not in the Caucasian population. At the same time, the results of a meta-analysis conducted by Aliakbari et al. (2020) revealed a significant risk of male infertility associated with the *MTHFR* C677T polymorphism in both the Asian and Caucasian populations (Aliakbari et al. 2020), and no correlation was established with the A1298C polymorphism. In contrast, a strong correlation between the A1298C polymorphism and severe oligozoospermia in the Indian population was determined by Singh et al. (2010). This polymorphism was considered a risk factor for male infertility in the Moroccan and Asian populations as well (Eloualid et al. 2012; Zhang et al. 2017). In support of these data, the results of our study revealed a trend for a significantly higher frequency of the homozygote C/C genotype (A1298C) in men with non-obstructive azoospermia. Simultaneously, we did not determine any considerable correlation between the C677T polymorphic variant and spermatogenic failure in our patients.

The allele and genotype frequencies of *MTHFR* A1298C and C677T polymorphisms vary among different geographical regions and ethnicities (Weiner et al. 2014; Nikzad et al. 2015; Zhang et al. and Hong et al. 2017; Ullah et al. 2018). People from different ethnic groups are exposed to various external factors, such as folate and vitamin B12 intake, supplementation with drugs, smoking, exposure to toxins, etc., that may alter the regulation of gene expression or lead to oxidative stress. It was observed that higher folic acid intake lowers the risk of hyperhomocysteinemia, associated with the *MTHFR* C677T polymorphism (Murphy et al. 2011). Folic acid supplementation in homozygote (T/T genotype) patients with severe oligozoospermia significantly improved their semen parameters and pregnancy outcome (Huang et al. 2019). The *MTHFR* A1298C polymorphism is not associated with hyperhomocysteinemia as the C677T variant, but changes in the folate status, DNA hypomethylation, DNA damage, increased lipid peroxidation, and alterations in the motility and morphology of male gametes were established in infertile men carrying the C/C homozygote genotype (Ledowsky

et al. 2021). Supplementation with folic acid and other antioxidants can reduce the oxidative stress levels and improve semen quality in such patients. Considering the external factors such as diet, folate and vitamins from group B intake, exposure to toxins and xenobiotics that affect testicular function, and the internal factors, especially the genetic ones, such as polymorphisms (different from *MTHFR*) or mutations in genes involved in spermatogenesis and spermiogenesis, a more extended and complex study is required to establish the correlation between *MTHFR* variants and male infertility.

Conclusions

Spermatogenesis is a complex process in which more than 2000 genes are involved. The folate and methionine cycles are crucial for germ cells' proliferation and are

strongly involved in spermatogenesis and spermiogenesis. Folate metabolism depends on distinct external and genetic factors, varying among different ethnic populations and geographical regions. Furthermore, in men with severe forms of infertility, more than one genetic finding (gene polymorphisms or mutations) is often established. Considering this, we can conclude that the impact of *MTHFR* polymorphisms on male infertility should be further investigated in correlation with other genetic and non-genetic factors interfering with the process of spermatogenesis.

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